

Total count	A, count	C, count	N, count	A, proportion	C, proportion	N, proportion	Protein class
48	34	13	1	71	27	2	Enzyme (kinase)
45	25	10	10	56	22	22	Enzyme (oxidoreductase)
43	29	13	1	67	30	2	Enzyme (transferase)
39	22	16	1	56	41	3	Enzyme (hydrolase)
21	9	12	0	43	57	0	TF (AP2-EREBP family)
19	11	6	2	58	32	11	TF (GRAS family)
18	14	4	0	78	22	0	TF (MYB-HB-like family)
17	1	16	0	6	94	0	TF (SBP family)
13	1	0	12	8	0	92	TF (C2C2-Dof family)
13	5	5	3	38	38	23	Transporter (substrate unknown)
12	8	3	1	67	25	8	TF (MADS-MIKC family)
11	3	4	4	27	36	36	TF (Hap3/NF-YB family)
10	5	3	2	50	30	20	F-box protein
10	8	1	1	80	10	10	TF (C2H2 family)
9	6	2	1	67	22	11	Peptide (cysteine-rich, NCR family)
9	2	7	0	22	78	0	TF (ARF family)
9	6	2	1	67	22	11	TF (bHLH family)
9	1	7	1	11	78	11	TF (Homeodomain-TALE-KNOX family)
8	4	4	0	50	50	0	Enzyme (ligase)
8	1	5	2	13	63	25	Peptide (CEP family)
302	224	46	32	74	15	11	Other
673	419	179	75	62	27	11	All

Figure 3. Different protein classes have different proportions of phenotypes, which may reflect their relative functional importance. Letters A, C, and N stand for altered, conditional, and neutral phenotypes, respectively. The graph shows only the top-20 protein classes. The complete list of protein classes and corresponding statistical analysis are available in Data S10. The summary on phenotypes of combined protein groups is available in Data S11.